

and organic C. The hot and humid climate favors rapid decomposition of organic matter and losses of C and N. This limits the yield potential of rice, even with high rates of N fertilizer.

Incorporating plant material with a narrow C:N ratio could help improve rice yield potential. We studied the effect of incorporating mungbean *Phaseolus aureus* Pulse residue on yield of rice cultivars PR106 and PR108.

Soil of the experimental field was alkaline and low in organic C and available N. Mungbean per hectare was seeded at 25 kg/ha the last week of Apr.

In one treatment, 65-d-old pods were picked and the residue was removed. In the second treatment, the residue was plowed 1 d before transplanting 35-d-old rice seedlings. N was applied at 0, 90, 120, and 150 kg/ha in three equal splits: at transplanting and at 21 d and 42 d after transplanting.

Mungbean yielded 650 kg grain and 3 t residue/ha. The residue contained about 60 kg N/ha.

Rice yields increased with N application in both treatments (see figure). Residue incorporation conspicuously

increased yield. Grain yield with 120 kg N/ha plus residue incorporation was comparable to that with 150 kg N/ha and no residue incorporated.

Residue incorporation produced yields equal to those at higher N application with no residue. Incorporating residue increased rice yield 30% when no fertilizer N was applied, but the increase decreased with increasing fertilizer N (see table). □

Grain yield of 2 rice cultivars with applied N, with and without incorporation of mungbean residue. Ludhiana, India.

Increase (%) in rice yields with legume residue incorporation. Ludhiana, India.

N levels (kg/ha)	Increase (%) in rice yield	
	PR106	PR108
0	31.1	35.1
60	20.3	21.7
90	10.7	18.2
120	9.0	9.4
150	8.3	7.3

Performance of rice + maize intercropping in a drought-prone situation

Numa Ibn Shams and M. A. Quddus, On-Farm Research Division, Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute, Joydebpur, Gazipur 1701, Bangladesh

Yield and profitability of upland rice in Bangladesh is relatively low (average 1 t/ha) because existing local cultivars have low yield potential and drought is intermittent during vegetative and reproductive phases. The yield potential of maize is relatively higher than that of upland rice, and it has some drought resistance. But maize as the only crop in the early summer season is not culturally acceptable.

We studied the effect of intercropping maize with broadcast upland rice in a field trial Apr-Jul 1988. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with six replications. Rice (cv. Hashikalmi) was broadcast at 100 kg seed/ha and maize (cv. Barnali) was interplanted in rows. Treatments were 1.5-, 2.0-, and 2.5-m

row spacing for maize, 25 cm between rows.

In maize alone and maize + rice, fertilizer was applied at 100-26-33 kg NPK/ha. In rice alone, urea, triple superphosphate, muriate of potash at 40-26-33 kg NPK/ha was applied.

Intercropped rice yields decreased significantly with all maize row spacing; rice yield was highest with 2.5-m row spacing of maize (see table). Intercropped maize yields were not statistically different at all row spacings, but were

significantly lower than that of maize alone. Combined yield (expressed as rice equivalent) was highest in maize alone, followed by that in rice - maize intercropped at 1.5-m row spacing.

The land equivalent ratio was more than 1.0 in all intercropping arrangements; the highest was at 2.5-m row spacing of maize. Highest total energy produced was obtained with maize alone (0.81×10^7 cal/ha), followed by maize at 2.5-m row spacing (0.74×10^7 cal/ha). Gross return and benefit:cost

Yield and economic return of maize + rice intercropping at Manikganj, Bangladesh, Apr-Jul 1988.

Treatment	Yield ^a (t/ha)		Rice-equivalent yield (t/ha)	Land equivalent ratio	Energy equivalent ^b (10^7 cal/ha)	Gross return (\$/ha)	Benefit:cost ratio
	Rice	Maize					
Rice alone	1.1 a	-	1.1	1.0	.40	174	1.25
Maize alone	-	2.3 a	2.3	1.0	.81	363	1.52
Rice + maize (1.5 × 0.25 m)	0.6 b	1.5 b	2.1	1.10	.64	329	1.34
Rice + maize (12.0 × 0.5 m)	0.6 b	1.4 b	2.0	1.14	.70	311	1.27
Rice + maize (2.5 × 0.5 m)	0.7 b	1.4 b	2.1	1.27	.74	326	1.35
CV (%)	14.6	6.7	-	-	-	-	-

^aIn a column under each condition, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bCaloric values for rice and maize were calculated as 360 and 349 calories/100g, respectively, considering 66% and 100% edible yield of unhusked rice and maize, respectively.

ratio were higher with maize alone, followed by maize at 2.5-m row spacing.

Rice - maize intercropping may be more profitable than rice alone. Further research is needed to select appropriate rice varieties and fertilizer management for the system. □

Performance of oilseed and pulse crops in a rice-based cropping sequence

G. Singh and O. P. Singh, Narendra Deva University of Agriculture and Technology, Crop Research Station, Ghagharaghat, Bahraich 271901, Uttar Pradesh (UP), India

Long-duration rice varieties and excess moisture delay sowing of dry season crops in the rainfed lowlands. Oilseeds and pulses are cultivated as relay or sequence crops, but yields are poor because of poor plant stands due to lack of adequate nutrients.

We studied the effect of seed rate and fertilizer on the productivity of a rice-based cropping system 1986-87 to 1988-89, in a randomized block design with four replications.

Economic analysis

Use of bullock power in rice production

T. R. Shanmugam, Veterinary College and Research Institute, Namakkal 637002, Tamil Nadu, India

Draft animal power is a critical component of rice-based cropping systems in Tamil Nadu. Rice requires more animal power than other crops because transplanting involves extensive tillage: plowing, puddling, bunding, and leveling. We studied the cost of draft animal power use on rice farms using 1971-72 to 1983-84 data from the scheme on Cost of Cultivation of Principal Crops (CCPC) covering the state's rice belt.

Bullock pair hours/ha fluctuate. Bullock costs/ha have increased (see table). But the proportion of total

Yields and net return^a of rice-based cropping systems in rainfed lowlands. Ghagharaghat, UP, India, 1986-89.^b

Treatment ^b	Grain yield (t/ha)		Cost (\$/ha)	Gross income (\$/ha)	Net return (\$/ha)	Benefit: cost ratio
	Rice	Second crop				
Rice alone	2.4	-	167	338	171	2.02
Rice - lentil + S ₁ F ₁	2.4	0.230	211	372	161	1.76
Rice - lentil + S ₁ F ₂	2.4	0.409	235	472	237	2.01
Rice - lentil + S ₂ F ₁	2.4	0.365	218	391	173	1.79
Rice - lentil + S ₂ F ₂	2.4	0.635	242	546	304	2.25
Rice - linseed + S ₁ F ₁	2.4	0.235	222	442	220	1.99
Rice - linseed + S ₁ F ₂	2.4	0.498	242	541	299	2.23
Rice - linseed + S ₂ F ₁	2.4	0.413	228	506	278	2.21
Rice - linseed + S ₂ F ₂	2.4	0.664	249	608	359	2.44
Rice - mustard + S ₁ F ₁	2.4	0.168	203	416	213	2.04
Rice - mustard + S ₁ F ₂	2.4	0.212	228	438	210	1.91
Rice - mustard + S ₂ F ₁	2.4	0.199	216	430	214	1.99
Rice - mustard + S ₂ F ₂	2.4	0.262	230	459	229	1.99

^a Av of 3 crop years. US\$1 = Rs 16.32. ^b S₁ = normal seed rate (kg/ha): linseed 30, lentil 40, mustard 5; S₂ = 50% extra seed than normal (kg/ha): linseed 45, lentil 60, mustard 7.50; F₁ = without fertilizer, F₂ = recommended fertilizer (pulses: 20 kg N + 17.6 kg P/ha) and (oilseeds: 30 kg N + 8.8 kg P/ha).

The experiment site had sandy to clay loam soil with pH 8.1, 0.38% organic C, 23.8 kg available P₂O₅, and 267 kg K₂O/ha. Rice variety Madhukar was transplanted the third week of Jul at 20- × 15-cm spacing with 40-20-20 kg NPK/ha. Lentil variety PL 406, linseed variety Mukta, and mustard variety Varuna were broadcast in the standing rice crop 8 d before harvest the last week of Nov.

All the dry season crops produced higher grain yields with higher seeding rates and fertilizer (see table). The highest net return was with rice - linseed at higher seeding rate + fertilizer (\$359/ha), followed by rice - lentil at higher seed rate + fertilizer (\$304/ha). Lowest net return was with rice - lentil at normal seeding rate without fertilizer. □

Bullock power use on Tamil Nadu rice farms.

Year	Cost of hired bullock (\$/ha)	Cost of owned bullock (\$/ha)	Total bullock cost (\$/ha)	Total bullock pair use (h/ha)	Total production cost (\$/ha)	Bullock cost: total cost (%)
1971-72	2.67	4.81	7.48	255.29	96.89	7.72
1972-73	(35.70) 2.17	(64.30) 3.51	5.68	283.34	92.36	6.15
1973-74	(38.20) 2.67	(61.80) 4.81	7.48	219.10	72.48	10.32
1974-75	(35.70) 4.41	(64.30) 6.91	11.32	199.77	197.90	5.72
1975-76	(38.96) 3.43	(61.04) 13.29	16.72	224.76	165.71	10.09
1976-77	(20.50) 2.06	(79.50) 17.39	19.45	230.65	166.52	11.68
1977-78	(10.59) 2.99	(89.41) 15.26	18.25	186.64	187.37	9.74
1978-79	(16.38) 3.87	(83.62) 17.97	21.84	231.61	219.28	9.96
1979-80	(17.72) 4.18	(82.28) 23.07	27.25	182.85	241.36	11.29
1980-81	(15.34) 3.05	(84.66) 22.31	25.36	203.80	259.84	9.76
1981-82	(12.02) 6.78 (24.91)	(87.98) 20.44 (75.09)	27.22	223.37	338.98	8.03
1982-83	3.85	32.15	36.00	251.29	422.04	8.53
1983-84	(10.69) 7.71 (28.29)	(89.31) 19.54 (71.71)	27.25	204.35	365.77	7.45

^a Figures in parentheses are percent of total bullock cost/ha.